

Application of innovative technologies in legal technical schools of the Ministry of Justice

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The purpose of the article is to analyze the experience of implementing innovative educational technologies in teaching students legal training areas. Modern requirements for training students in jurisprudence areas of preparation determine the relevance of using innovative educational technologies in this process. Innovative technologies play an important role in the process of training lawyers. Innovative educational technologies contribute to more rapid and high-quality formation of students' competence. Innovative technologies are a system of teaching methods and techniques aimed at achieving positive educational results through the implementation of the established algorithm of actions. The experience of students' participation in legal competitions and conferences was also studied. According to the requirements of the Federal state standard of higher education, educational technologies must be used in the preparation of students. Several levels of training were identified: high, medium, low. A high level of training is typical for students who are fully aware of the role and place of a lawyer in society. He has a sufficient amount of professional knowledge and strives for constant self-improvement and development of additional competencies in the field of law. When students study a cycle of professional disciplines, innovative educational technologies are implemented (case technologies, project technologies, game technologies, information technologies, and others). Analyzing innovative technologies in the framework of professional training of students, the authors of the article highlight their features. The work demonstrates the results of a study on

the implementation of innovative technologies in the educational process of a higher educational institution. Modern educational technologies are a perspective way to improve the quality of education of students in legal areas of training.

Keywords: educational technologies, innovative technologies, jurisprudence training, professional training.

Increasing the legal awareness of citizens is a strategic goal of the modern state, in the implementation of which a huge role belongs to the system of education, especially higher education. The state takes measures aimed at increasing legal education (new curricula corresponding to established state standards, propaganda of legal knowledge in the media, etc.), but they do not give the proper result - the legal culture of a large number of students remains low, including who have completed their studies. Traditional theoretical training, aimed at obtaining students only theoretical legal knowledge, has shown its insufficient effectiveness. The modern labor market requires the system of higher education to form students' practical competencies so that the graduate has the functionality of a trained specialist in the relevant field of activity. The authors of the article emphasize that legal education for non-core students should use other methods of teaching that are different from those used in the training of law students. The results of the research allow us to offer innovative technologies for teaching legal disciplines to students of non-core professions in order to increase their legal literacy. The study may be of interest to students and teachers of secondary specialized institutions and universities in the relevant fields. Training in the field of jurisprudence occupies a significant place in the vocational training system. The state and society need highly qualified lawyers. And every year this demand is growing. The modern states are characterized by social and economic development, dynamics of political processes, appeal to the formation of an initiative personality, its active formation not only in a pedagogical environment, but also in a broad social environment.

Among the main strategic goals of their socio-economic policy is included, besides ensuring economic growth and strengthening the country's external competitiveness, increasing the legal awareness of citizens. Today, the economic growth of countries and their social progress are hampered by acute problems with legality, the level of offenses and crimes, corruption, and imperfection of the judicial system. One of the reasons for these negative phenomena is undoubtedly the low legal culture and insufficient legal education of citizens. For the implementation of high-quality training of students in jurisprudence areas of preparation, modern methods, tools and technologies are required. The consequence of institutional and informational structural transformations in the economy was the modernization of the system of domestic education, ensuring the formation of the professional competence of students. Higher education institutions are searching for modern methods, tools and technologies for more rapid achievement of educational goals. Numerous studies have allowed modern scientists to identify the benefits of innovative technologies in these conditions. They guarantee the step-by-step achievement of the set goals. The use of innovative technologies in the training of modern lawyers allows you to create the necessary professional competencies and prepare a specialist capable of productive activities (Oros et al., 2018). The use of innovative technologies in teaching students should be considered as a tool conducive to the implementation of the new educational paradigm (Vaganova et al., 2019a). In this context, innovative technologies contribute to the training of a modern specialist who can creatively carry out professional activities in rapidly changing conditions. In this article, we consider the implementation of innovative technologies in the training of students in legal fields.

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